
AI Act: *Ex ante* problems of *ex ante* regulation

Jakob Mišič Jančar^{1,#}, Vid Lobnik^{1,#}, David Ljube^{1,#}, Marko Jeran^{2,*}

- ^{1.} University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Law, Ljubljana, Slovenia
^{2.} “Jožef Stefan” Institute, Department of Inorganic Chemistry and Technology, Ljubljana, Slovenia
[#] MJ, VL and DL contributed equally to this work
^{*} Correspondence: MJ, marko.jeran@ijs.si

Abstract: The article provides a detailed examination of the European Union's Artificial Intelligence (AI) Act, emphasizing its aim to create a safe, ethical, and innovative digital environment by implementing a risk-based regulatory framework for AI technologies. It discusses the categorization of AI systems according to their potential societal risks, the foundational legal principles from the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) it builds upon, and the specific provisions for *ex ante* risk assessments to ensure compliance with fundamental rights, transparency, and accountability. Additionally, the article highlights the establishment of the European AI Office as a step towards the Act's enforcement and its broader role in the EU's Digital Strategy, aiming to harmonize AI practices across member states while protecting citizens' rights and fostering global standards for AI regulation.

Keywords: AI Act, AI Regulatory framework, Fundamental rights, EU Digital Strategy, Risk assessments, High-risk AI, European AI Office, Overregulation

1. Introduction

This document presents the findings of an in-depth study analysing the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council (*AI Act proposal 1*) laying down harmonised rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts. The research delves into the intricacies of the proposed regulation, assessing its implications and potential impact on the future of AI governance within the European Union. The proposal for European Union's Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) represents a landmark initiative aimed at establishing a comprehensive regulatory framework for artificial intelligence (AI) within the EU. As digital technologies increasingly permeate every aspect of our lives (Bell, 2021), the EU seeks to harness the benefits of AI while safeguarding fundamental rights and ensuring safety. This article delves into the essence of the AI Act, exploring its integration into the EU's constitutional scheme, its core requirements and protections, the fundamental and human rights it seeks to uphold, and the transformative impact it anticipates on the AI landscape.

2. What is the AI Act?

The European Parliament Resolution on a Framework of Ethical Aspects of Artificial Intelligence, Robotics and Related Technologies specifically recommends to the Commission to propose legislative action to harness the opportunities and benefits of AI, but also to ensure protection of ethical principles (*Resolution 1, point 4*).

At the heart of the AI Act is a risk-based regulatory strategy, which meticulously categorises AI systems according to the potential threats they pose. This stratification ranges from those that present unacceptable risks to society to those deemed of minimal concern. This approach is emblematic of the EU's intention to foster a digital environment where technology serves the public good while adhering to ethical standards and respecting human dignity and autonomy (*Resolution 1, point 9*).

The legal foundation of the AI Act is etched in the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), drawing upon Articles 16 and 114. These provisions empower the EU to enact measures ensuring the seamless functioning of the internal market. The Act underscores the EU's ambition to cement its stance as a global leader in the ethical deployment of AI, ensuring that such technologies thrive within a framework that champions human rights, transparency, and accountability (*Resolution 1, point 11*).

3. Ex ante risk assessments

When something exists in the legal system that lacks legal personality but has actual and legal consequences on its environment, the question of responsibility immediately arises. Who in the legal system will be accountable for something that cannot guarantee for itself? An individual is responsible for the consequences of their actions, and in some cases, may be held objectively liable due to their duties or position. However, the challenge of accountability for something that, in terms of subjectivity, is similar to an animal, but in legal power, can be equivalent to a judge in the right situation, presents a complex issue. Attention of AI is a complex algorithmic procedure that often does not act in a way that can be exactly traced back (Vaswani, 2023). Beside benefits of AI that are Uncovering Historical Patterns of Bias, Cost-Savings, Efficiency (Ajunwa, 2023) we also must manage risk that comes with it. To prevent situations in which these quasi entities would gain power and infringe upon the fundamental rights, the AI Act introduces a risk assessment. Therefore, artificial intelligence that is developed for decision-making in risky areas or could be used there is marked with a certain level of risk. This indicates the danger of

automated governance (for term clarification see Ajunwa, 2023, p. 361) and attempts to preemptively prevent contentious situations from occurring. So how does this system work? The classification of risk within the AI Act operates through a nuanced, risk-based approach, dividing AI systems into different categories based on the level of threat they may pose. This framework meticulously outlines a spectrum from minimal to unacceptable risk, placing AI applications within this continuum according to their potential impact on society and individual rights. Central to this risk assessment is the Act's commitment to protecting public safety, consumer rights, and fundamental EU values. It meticulously identifies high-risk AI systems that require stringent compliance with predefined criteria before they can be marketed or put into use across the EU.

1. Unacceptable Risk Prohibited in development and distribution are considered AI systems presenting an unacceptable risk. This will ensure that AI technologies that are inherently harmful do not make their way to the market (*AI Act proposal 1, chapter 5.2.*).
2. High Risk Requirements addressed to the providers of high-risk AI systems themselves, based on data governance, documentation, transparency, and human oversight. In addition, the systems would have to be capable of obtaining a positive verdict of conformity assessment from a notified body or national authorities (*AI Act proposal 1, chapter 5.2.*).
3. Limited and Minimal Risk The systems' level of AI that would be categorised into low and minimal risk would have fewer regulatory burdens, mainly ensuring transparency in operation and making available to the users all the necessary information relating to the functioning of the AI system (*AI Act proposal 1, chapter 5.2.*).

The implications of receiving a high-risk designation for an AI system are profound. It subjects the AI system to stringent regulatory oversight, including compliance with mandatory risk management and mitigation measures, data governance standards, transparency obligations, and mechanisms for human oversight. These requirements are not merely procedural; they are designed to instil a foundational level of trust and safety in AI technologies, aligning their operation with the Union's values and principles (*AI Act proposal 1, chapter 5.2.3.*).

The duty to conduct these assessments falls squarely on the shoulders of AI system providers. These entities, whether based within the EU or operating from outside its borders but targeting the EU market, are obligated to ensure that their AI systems undergo a comprehensive evaluation against the specified criteria laid out in the Act. The Act also empowers Commission and national authorities through the establishment of an EU-wide database for stand-alone high-risk AI systems with mainly fundamental rights implications. The database will be operated by the Commission and provided with data by the providers of the AI systems, who will be required to register their systems before placing them on the market or otherwise putting them into service (*AI Act proposal 1, chapter 5.2.6.*).

4. Consideration of Fundamental Rights in the AI Act

Fundamental rights are tackled in the AI act in multiple ways. The explanatory memorandum to the final proposal of the AI Act describes the document as "human centric" (*AI Act proposal 1, chapter 1.1.*), having high regard for fundamental rights.

The draft identifies potential risks to human rights due to unpredictability and autonomous behaviour of certain AI systems and aims at ensuring their compatibility with the former (*Council note, clause 5*). Two of the four points comprising the Commission's specific objectives emphasise care for the human rights aspect of AI regulation, namely ensuring consistency with existing law and enabling its effective enforcement (*AI Act proposal 1, chapter 1.1*).

As follows from preparatory documentation, respect of human rights is established by ensuring consistency of the document with both the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (hereinafter: the Charter) and secondary legislation on data protection, consumer protection, non-discrimination and gender equality while also complementing existing non-discrimination instruments (*AI Act proposal 1, chapter 1.2*). The issue arising regarding this legislation is the seemingly horizontal application of fundamental rights enshrined in the Charter. As established in its Article 51, the Charter does not mention private entities as passive addressees of the Charter (Booklet 1 eNACT Project, 2020, p. 6). Article 16 of the Final Draft nevertheless bestows the obligations stemming from the Charter upon all providers (As defined in para. 2 of Article 3 of the *AI Act proposal 1*, the notion of 'provider' encompasses both public and private entities, including individuals) of high-risk AI systems, such as the duty to inform users of potential risks to fundamental rights in Article 13(3)(b)(iii) of the Final Draft. Invocation of fundamental rights in secondary legislation is present in other secondary legislation as well, e.g. the *Regulation GDPR*. However, in contrast to the AI act, the *Regulation GDPR* does not address observation of human rights upon private persons. In other words, the Charter as referred to in the AI Act now plays the role of a key instrument securing balance between human rights and economic considerations.

More importantly, as the European legislator assumes its own competence to establish this balance, the national courts and the ECtHR may play a proportionally reduced role when considering human rights in the field of AI. In the context of ECHR and its case law, the Charter itself limits the possibility of discrepancies through its Article 53(2), stating that the Charter shall not offer lesser protection than the ECHR, insofar as corresponding rights are concerned; on the other hand, the autonomy of national bodies to guarantee a higher standard of human rights protection in the field of AI is limited as it must be coordinated with the standards set by the CJEU in respect of the corresponding provisions of the Charter (See also Storgaard, 2015, p. 493).

The explanatory memorandum to the AI Act lists fundamental rights which may be most at risk due to AI activity: these are especially the right to human dignity, respect for private life and protection of personal data, non-discrimination, and equality between women and men, while aiming to "prevent a chilling effect on the rights to freedom of expression (Article 11) and freedom of assembly (Article 12)" (*AI Act proposal 1, chapter 3.5*.) and safeguarding procedural rights. Seeking to minimise the risk of erroneous or biased AI-assisted decisions regarding the latter, the memorandum does not seem to differentiate between obligations of private organisations (e.g. regarding employment) and institutions exercising public authority (citing law enforcement and the judiciary).

The document also references the rights of certain groups of people, such as workers, children, and persons with disabilities. Additionally, it mentions the right to a high level of environmental protection and the improvement of the quality of the environment. It is of course questionable how this right may be invoked in a private context.

Article 7 of the AI Act intrinsically links the risk assessment system to the notion of fundamental rights. High-risk AI systems are defined as AI systems intended to be

used in points 1 to 8 of Annex III to the AI Act where risks of adverse impact on fundamental rights is equivalent or greater than posed by systems already listed as high-risk in that same Annex. As follows from the second paragraph of the same Article, the assessment of such harm is to be conducted by the Commission in consideration of the conditions enumerated therein by the European Legislator, i. a. the extent and gravity of the harm already caused to fundamental rights and of the potential future harm.

Article 52(3) of the Final Draft references rights to freedom of expression and to freedom of arts and sciences guaranteed in the Charter as exceptions to transparency obligations for certain AI systems, leaving the door open to the highly polemic topic of artistic expression by means of AI-generated works (For an overview of currently open questions regarding this topic see i.a. Škiljić, 2021). By acquisition the answer to the question of authorship in this context may be provided by the European legislator and the CJEU - an EU wide approach may be necessary for certain issues of authorship as per CJEU case-law while the remaining aspects are covered by laws of the Member States (Fritz, 2024, p. 3 and the case-law cited therein; see the same text regarding certain considerations on AI authorship). Whether and to what extent the regulation of authorship in AI contexts on the European level is necessary and in line with subsidiarity considerations expressed in the Final draft is a topic that will be addressed in a future text.

Article 41 of the Final Draft empowers the Commission to adopt implementing acts regarding specific safety or fundamental rights concerns. In addition to the clash between national and EU human rights standards, this provision bestows limited decision-making regarding human rights issues upon the executive branch of the EU institutions. Whether such delegation of powers is justified and sensible is a consideration that should be addressed, but would vastly exceed the intention of this brief article.

5. AI Act as part of the EU Digital Strategy

The AI Act is one of the acts passed by the European Parliament and Commission as a part of the EU Digital Strategy. A Europe fit for the digital age is one of the European Commission's six political priorities and AI Act tries to establish exactly that, to prepare EU countries on the fast-approaching AI Challenges. The AI Act is quite ambitious with its goals and is trying to create a framework or building blocks on which further regulation of AI is going to be built by EU member states themselves or by the EU Parliament and Commission.

The EU is trying to ambitiously create a truly comprehensive legal environment for further development of AI systems, as of now, the EU stands as a pioneering global actor in this endeavour. The EU regulations do not stop at the border of the EU as they have an important impact even outside the EU borders. The so-called Brussels effect is the process where regulations by the EU de facto externalise outside the EU borders through market mechanisms (Bradford, 2020, p. 232). A notable example of this impact is the 2016 General Data Protection Regulation (*Regulation GDPR*), which prompted major technology companies to revise their terms of service to comply with EU standards and continue operating within the EU market. As the EU introduces the AI Act, it remains to be seen whether similar global consequences will unfold for AI industry leaders, but it is already established that the AI Act is going to change the way developers and end users experience AI development.

5.1. The European AI Office

The AI Act will introduce new requirements for AI systems as such the EU has established a new regulatory body “The European AI Office” within the European Commission. The primary objective of this office is to play a key role in implementing the AI Act. Specifically, it will enforce rules related to general-purpose AI models. The AI Office will collaborate with governance bodies in EU Member States, evaluate AI models, request information from model providers, and wield the authority to apply sanctions when necessary. Its pivotal role ensures the effective implementation and enforcement of AI regulations across the EU.

5.2. AI Act Impact assessment

The EU Parliament and Commission conducted an impact assessment (similar OECD, 2019) for the accepted AI Act in which they also touch upon the expected compliance costs. The EU bodies understand that by increasing costs for companies and end users they are also creating blockades for further and faster development (Similar *Regulation GDPR*). The final EU AI Act was prepared with major stakeholders and several of them warned the EU to avoid duplication, conflicting obligations and overregulation (*AI Act proposal 1, introductory clause 63*). With that in mind, they decided for the approach that would implore Horizontal EU legislative instruments following a proportionate risk-based approach in coordination with codes of conduct for non-high-risk AI systems. The risk assessment states that this approach will increase people’s trust in AI and companies will gain in legal certainty and with that the EU will continue to develop “fast-growing AI ecosystems” (*AI Act proposal 1, chapter 3.3.*).

6. Conclusion

The European Union's Artificial Intelligence (AI) Act embodies a pioneering stride toward sculpting a secure, ethical, and innovation-friendly digital landscape. Anchored in the EU's broader Digital Strategy, the Act lays a robust foundation for the governance of AI technologies, ensuring they align with the Union's core values of human dignity, privacy, transparency, and non-discrimination. By instituting a risk-based regulatory framework, the AI Act navigates the delicate balance between fostering technological innovation and safeguarding fundamental rights and public safety while striving towards development of ethical AI (more Rubenstein, 2021). The establishment of the European AI Office underlines the EU's commitment to rigorous enforcement and effective implementation of the Act, signifying a pivotal step towards harmonising AI practices across the member states and potentially influencing global standards for AI regulation. As the AI landscape continues to evolve, the AI Act stands as a testament to the EU's proactive approach in embracing the digital future while steadfastly protecting the rights and well-being of its citizens.

Let us emphasise that the research has so far uncovered many issues that will be analysed in much greater detail in the further steps of the study.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

List of regulation documents

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